

UNTANGLING DECARBONIZATION STRATEGIES FOR NET ZERO CARBON FIBER

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ABSTRACT

The production of polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based carbon fibre (CF) is highly energy-intensive, contributing significantly to its embodied carbon. With global demand for CF projected to more than double by 2030, reducing the global warming potential (GWP) of CF manufacturing is critical to supporting the decarbonisation of transport, energy, and industrial sectors. This study presents a life cycle assessment (LCA) to evaluate the cradle-to-gate GWP of PAN-based CF production, with a UK-specific case study, and explores a range of decarbonisation strategies including energy efficiency, electrification, and green gas substitution.

The LCA identifies major GWP hotspots across precursor and fibre production stages, particularly during high-temperature oxidation and carbonisation processes. Electrification of these stages, powered by low-carbon electricity, offers the most immediate and impactful emissions reductions. However, abatement systems for hazardous exhausts remain a key technical challenge. Complementary strategies include the adoption of bio-based acrylonitrile (Bio-ACN), energy recovery technologies, and the substitution of natural gas with BioMethane or eMethane.

Scenario modelling using projected UK grid decarbonisation pathways reveals that electrification delivers the fastest route to net zero CF production. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of decarbonisation varies with regional grid composition, underlining the importance of site-specific strategies. A multi-horizon roadmap is proposed, outlining near-, mid-, and long-term actions to support CF producers in aligning technology development with emissions reduction goals. This study provides a foundation for industry and policy stakeholders to prioritise interventions and accelerate the transition toward low-carbon CF manufacturing.

1 INTRODUCTION

The current global demand for carbon fibre (CF) is estimated to be 115 kt per year as of 2023, and projected to grow to 280 kt per year by 2030 [1]. While lightweighting using carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) has played a critical role in transportation decarbonisation, CFRP is now required for decarbonised energy generation and storage solutions. Despite the high-performance benefits of CF, its production is highly energy-intensive, resulting in significant embodied carbon. Sphera Managed LCA Content reports that the globally aggregated global warming potential (GWP) of polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based CF can reach up to 35 kg CO₂e. per kg of CF produced [2]. Considering global CF demand in 2023 (115 kt, [1]) and current GWP of PAN-based CF, the global demand for CF is projected to generate up to 4 Mt CO₂e annually. To enable the further decarbonisation of transportation and renewable energy sectors, it is imperative to reduce the GWP associated with CF production.

The CF production process consists of several energy-intensive stages, including PAN fibre precursor production, stabilisation/oxidation, carbonisation, and surface treatment, all of which contribute to the overall embodied energy. Michaud et al. reviewed the literature and reported a wide range of energy

consumption values, from 171 to 1169 MJ per kg of CF produced. Dér et al. [3] compiled energy consumption data for each stage of production from various sources, noting that energy requirements for producing PAN-based precursors range from 245 to 394 MJ per kg of PAN [4][5], while the energy demands for manufacturing CF itself range from 219 to 704 MJ per kg of CF [4][5][6][7]. Carbonisation is the most energy-demanding phase [8], where the stabilised fibres are heated in an inert atmosphere at extremely high temperatures, typically between 1000 °C and 2000 °C.

Lifecycle assessment (LCA) is a widely used method to evaluate the environmental impacts of a product throughout part or all of its life cycle, from raw material extraction through to disposal or recycling. In the case of CF, LCA is particularly important as it enables a thorough evaluation of the material's high energy consumption during production, as well as its potential environmental advantages, such as reduced weight in transportation applications. Multiple studies have employed LCA to assess the GWP of CF production [4][9][10], with reported values ranging from 12.2 to 55.8 kg CO₂e per kg of CF [11]. Although there is significant variability in the literature, the GWP of CF remains substantially higher than that of other commonly used structural materials [12]. This elevated GWP is primarily driven by the significant energy demand during production, which is met by fossil fuels, through the regional electricity grid and / or the direct combustion of natural gas during high temperature manufacturing stages. The GWP of CF production is therefore dominated by three sources: 1) GHG emissions associated with grid electricity generation used to power the high temperature ovens, 2) direct GHG emissions associated with NG combustion in the high temperature ovens and abatement systems, and 3) the GHG emissions associated with PAN fibre precursor production [4][3][8][13][14][15].

In addition to developing lower impact precursor materials, strategies to reduce the embodied carbon of CF products should therefore reduce the energy demand of CF production and/or use decarbonised energy sources. The former will likely require adaptation of legacy or development of a new generation of CF production lines which are able to operate at higher energy efficiency. On the other hand, the latter may be achievable passively through the transition to renewable energy sources.

Several authors have investigated interventions to mitigate the impact from energy used during CF production. Prenzel et al. found that the energy consumption is responsible for 59% of the climate change associated with CF manufacturing, which can be reduced by 53% by transitioning to renewable electricity [16]. Strózyk et al. demonstrated a 67% reduction in energy demand during CF production through the utilisation of microwave heating, when compared to conventional heating technologies [17]. Reducing processing time for CF production, such as rapid oxidation, has demonstrated a 70% reduction in energy required for fibre oxidation [18].

Recent research into CF production has explored alternatives to the traditional PAN precursor, focusing on non-PAN and bio-based materials to reduce the high energy consumption and GWP associated with CF manufacturing. PAN can be made from bio-based sources, creating a potential drop-in replacement for the CF manufacturing process. Bio-derived acrylonitrile (Bio-ACN) has been studied for several years [19][20][21][22], and can be produced from biomass waste using various methodologies described in [23]. Bio-ACN production using wood-based biomass has been licensed by Trillium Renewable Chemicals who are working with Solvay to assess Bio-ACN as a drop-in replacement for petroleum-based ACN in PAN fibre production [24][25].

There is currently limited data available on the GWP of Bio-ACN production, and the authors were unable to find specific GWP data for CF products manufactured using Bio-ACN as a precursor. Goyal reported the GWP of Bio-ACN produced from sugars through a three-stage process involving hydrocracking, dehydration, and ammoxidation [20]. The GWP of Bio-ACN was found to be 0.29 kg CO₂e per kg of Bio-ACN, representing a substantial reduction compared to ACN derived from crude oil, which has a reported GWP of 6.05 kg CO₂e per kg of ACN. Goyal also used scanning electron microscopy to compare the morphology of CFs produced using Bio-ACN and standard crude oil-derived ACN, observing no significant differences in fibre shape or structure [20]. However, mechanical properties were not tested, leaving it uncertain whether the use of Bio-ACN affects the mechanical performance of the resulting CFs.

While many studies have used LCA to assess the impact of CF production, no studies have quantified and compared the impact of prominent decarbonisation strategies. This study aims to examine how the cradle-to-gate GWP of PAN-based CF production may be reduced through the adoption of green energy solutions. Using LCA, it seeks to identify GWP hotspots in a UK case study to provide insights that

could inform global decarbonisation strategies for CF production. The LCA also models upstream production of raw materials, ammonia, ACN, and PAN fibres, to account for future energy scenarios on CF raw materials impact. The impact of using BioMethane, and synthetic methane (eMethane) in place of NG were also assessed. Additionally, the UK's Net Zero roadmap was used to assess how the transition to net zero grid power and electrification will affect GWP of CF production. Multivariable analysis was used to rank solutions for CF decarbonisation up to the year 2050 and identify optimal timelines for deploying decarbonisation solutions.

2 METHODOLOGY

This work has been conducted with reference to the methods provided in the international standards series ISO 14040 related to the preparation of LCA [26]. LCA is a standardised approach to evaluating the environmental impacts of a product over its life cycle. For CF production, the LCA methodology involves four key stages: goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory (LCI), impact assessment, and interpretation. The goal and scope stage outlines the purpose of the study and sets the system boundaries. This is followed by the impact assessment, which quantifies environmental effects such as GWP. Finally, in the interpretation phase, the results are analysed to identify opportunities for reducing environmental impacts, making LCA essential for improving the sustainability of CF production.

2.1 Goal and scope

The primary aim of the LCA is to evaluate the cradle-to-gate GWP of PAN based CF production, and to assess the potential of green energy solutions to reduce the GWP of CF production. The UK was used as a case study; however, it is the ambition to provide insight that can inform CF decarbonisation strategies globally. The LCA aims to evaluate the CF production phases and upstream processes to produce the feedstock materials for CF production. It is intended to find GWP hotspots and direct future sustainable development to mitigate these.

The following developments have been included in the analysis:

- Future electricity grid mix used in the production of CF and raw materials ACN and PAN fibre.
- Replacing NG with BioMethane for ACN, PAN, and CF production.
- Replacing NG with eMethane for ACN, PAN, and CF production.
- Electrification of processes utilising NG in ACN, PAN, and CF production.

2.2 Functional unit

The main function of structural CF is to provide strength and stiffness in composite materials. CF are produced at various grades; therefore, do not all provide the same reinforcement potential. The scope of this study is limited to assessing a single CF grade in isolation to maintain functionality across the scenarios. The Functional Unit for this LCA study is defined as: the production of 1 kg of CF. The reference flow for the study is 1 kg of CF.

2.3 Processes

Figure 1 depicts a simplified process flow for the current production of CF products, including the upstream production of petrochemical precursors. Methyl acrylate and ACN are the key components in the production of PAN fibres, which undergo thermal treatment in high-temperature ovens to yield CF. Subsequently, the CF is subjected to surface treatment and sizing. The various processes are presented in more detail in the authors' previous publication [27].

Figure 1 Process flow for CF production, including upstream production of petrochemical precursors

2.4 Lifecycle impact assessment

In accordance with the defined LCA goal and scope, this study as focused on the following Environmental Impact Indicator: Global Warming Potential (GWP 100 years) [kg CO_{2e}.].

2.5 System boundary, Lifecycle inventory, Allocation, Cut-off criteria

Refer to the authors' previous LCA publication for details on the system boundary, life cycle inventory, allocation methods, and cut-off criteria [27].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Energy consumption breakdown: PAN and carbon fibre production

Figure 2 shows a representative energy consumption breakdown for PAN fibre and CF production, based on the use of electrified oxidation and carbonisation ovens in CF manufacturing. The percentages reflect the share of total energy demand per unit mass of CF produced, including both PAN fibre and CF production stages. Natural gas use in PAN fibre production—mainly for solvent recovery at temperatures below 200 °C—and for CF drying, can be readily electrified.

A key barrier to full electrification lies in the abatement systems used to treat emissions from the oxidation and carbonisation ovens. For example, hydrogen cyanide (HCN), a hazardous byproduct, requires treatment at temperatures up to 1000 °C to ensure complete combustion, leading to high natural gas consumption. This accounts for approximately 28% of the total energy demand across PAN and CF production, representing the critical "hard-to-decarbonise" energy source.

Energy efficiency gains in abatement systems could be achieved by reducing airflow and integrating regenerative thermal oxidizers (RTOs) for oxidation oven exhaust, which are effective for high-airflow, moderate-VOC streams and can recover up to 95% of heat. However, while these approaches lower natural gas use, they do not fully eliminate the resulting GHG emissions and must be combined with

broader decarbonisation strategies. Potentially more challenging to decarbonise is the use of direct-fired thermal oxidizers (DFTOs) for low-flow, high-VOC exhaust streams, such as those from the carbonisation furnace. While DFTOs effectively treat tar-rich and HCN-laden emissions, they lack heat recovery and consume more fuel, contributing significantly to the remaining natural gas demand in CF production.

Figure 2 Representative energy consumption breakdown for CF production using electrified oxidation and carbonisation ovens

3.2 Impact of decarbonisation strategies

Figure 3 presents a comparison of various CF decarbonisation pathways, including electrification, BioMethane, and eMethane strategies, building on previous studies [27]. The assessment assumes the UK National Grid ESO projection for decarbonising electricity to net zero by 2050. In each scenario, natural gas is replaced on an energy-equivalent basis by the respective alternative energy source. The use of bio-based acrylonitrile is also assumed, as it is essential for achieving fully net zero CF products (discussed in more detail in author's previous publication [27]).

Figure 3 shows that electrification offers the fastest route to net zero CF production and should be prioritised by manufacturers. While electrification may necessitate substantial modifications to existing equipment currently reliant on natural gas, these upgrades are within the control of CF producers and do not depend on the future scalability of emerging technologies, such as BioMethane and eMethane. Although initial retrofit costs may be significant, electrification offers the potential for long-term cost savings through more efficient use of renewable electricity and can deliver considerable emissions reductions, positioning it as a viable and strategic decarbonisation pathway as technology and renewable energy infrastructure continue to advance.

Figure 3 also evaluates a 50% reduction in electricity demand (dashed green line), reflecting the potential of technologies such as microwave heating and rapid oxidation, which have demonstrated energy savings of up to 67% [17] and 70% [18], respectively. Early adoption of these energy efficiency measures is key, as they offer the most impact while the electricity grid is still carbon intensive. Beyond 2040, as the grid approaches net zero emissions, the primary motivation for further energy reductions will shift from carbon savings to economic benefits.

For processes where electrification faces technical challenges—such as exhaust gas treatment in abatement systems—green gas options may offer viable alternatives. In the near term (5–10 years), BioMethane is favoured over eMethane due to its independence from net zero electricity. However, in the long term, eMethane may offer greater emissions reductions as low-carbon electricity becomes more

accessible. In the near term, particularly within the UK, CF producers can support decarbonisation by purchasing gas backed by Renewable Gas Guarantees of Origin (RGGOs), facilitating market-based allocation of BioMethane, which currently comprises a small share of the national gas supply.

Figure 3 shows that net zero CF production is possible with synthetic methane; however, eMethane is expected to remain significantly more expensive than natural gas due to the energy demands of green hydrogen and CO₂ capture [28]. Given its uncertain viability and timeline, sole reliance on eMethane is high-risk. CF producers should instead prioritise electrification, process efficiency, and heat recovery to enable a more resilient decarbonisation pathway. Hydrogen combustion offers a potential alternative, bypassing the need for CO₂ capture, though the required process modifications are still unclear. While synthetic fuels are compatible with existing systems, their high cost and limited scalability reinforce the need for a balanced strategy—advancing fuel technologies while focusing on near-term, demand-side solutions.

Figure 3 Comparison of electrification and green gas solutions on CF production decarbonisation (assumes electrification of heat from natural gas in PAN and CF production processes on an equal calorie basis)

3.3 Accelerating emissions reduction through electrification

It is important to note that the effectiveness of electrification in reducing CF GWP depends heavily on the regional energy mix. In the UK, where the electricity grid already contains a high share of renewables, electrification leads to lower GWP. In contrast, in regions with fossil fuel-dominant grids, direct natural gas use for heat may result in lower GWP than electricity-based alternatives. This highlights the need for region-specific assessments and decarbonisation roadmaps that reflect local energy infrastructure and grid composition.

Moreover, the future electricity grid compositions remain uncertain, and the projections in Figure 3 are based on average grid mix scenarios. Even when considering the UK as a sole case study, there are large uncertainties in the timeline for grid scale renewable deployment which poses challenges in precisely mapping out the decarbonisation trajectory for CF. Relying passively on network level transition leaves CF producers with little control over the timing of net zero energy generation,

introducing uncertainty into decarbonisation roadmaps. To address this uncertainty and actively expedite the decarbonisation of their electricity consumption, CF producers could incorporate local or onsite renewable electricity generation technologies, such as solar or wind power, to displace some or all the grid electricity used. An example being SGL Carbon Fibers Ltd.'s Moses Lake site, which purchases renewable energy from local hydropower plants [29].

Electrified thermal oxidisers present a potential pathway to decarbonise high-temperature exhaust gas treatment in CF production by eliminating the need for natural gas or synthetic fuels / green gases in current abatement systems. When powered by low-carbon electricity, these systems could mitigate GHG emissions associated with thermal energy used for gas cleaning. Electrified RTOs (eRTO) are commercially available and may be suited for oxidation oven exhaust treatment. Electrically powered flameless thermal oxidisers (eTO) may also replace DFTOs currently used for high-temperature, high-VOC exhaust streams from carbonisation ovens. While promising, these technologies have not yet been deployed in CF production, and their ability to safely and reliably process hazardous emissions such as HCN and tar-laden streams remains unproven. Further research, pilot-scale trials, and performance validation of eRTO and eTOs under CF production conditions are required to determine their technical feasibility and facilitate industry uptake. Key barriers to implementation include likely higher upfront capital costs compared to conventional gas-fired systems, the potential need for complete system redesigns when retrofitting existing infrastructure, and grid constraints that may necessitate upgrades or energy storage solutions to manage peak electricity demand.

3.4 Multi-horizon CF decarbonisation strategy

Figure 4 presents a multi-horizon strategy for CF production decarbonisation, encompassing energy sourcing, technology development, and deployment timelines. This roadmap is designed to provide high-level guidance and actionable steps for CF producers aiming to transition towards net zero carbon fibre products. It integrates the carbon footprints of the various decarbonisation strategies assessed in this study alongside pragmatic considerations of the current and emerging technology landscape, market readiness, and infrastructure requirements. By aligning near-, mid-, and long-term actions with both impact potential and feasibility, the strategy supports informed decision-making and prioritisation of interventions that can accelerate progress toward net zero CF production.

Energy strategy

- Ahead of the UK grid reaching net zero emissions, CF producers should procure electricity backed by Renewable Energy Guarantees of Origin (REGOs) to both support the growth of renewable energy and achieve net zero electricity consumption through market-based allocation. Additionally, producers should explore opportunities for on-site renewable energy generation at existing facilities or consider siting new developments in regions with access to local renewable resources to further accelerate decarbonisation.
- While electrified solutions for hard-to-decarbonise processes—such as exhaust gas treatment—are under development, CF producers should purchase gas backed by Renewable Gas Guarantees of Origin (RGGOs) to support the expansion of green gas production and achieve net zero gas consumption through market-based mechanisms.

Technology deployment

- CF producers should transition to PAN fibre suppliers utilising bio-based acrylonitrile feedstocks. This advanced technology is anticipated to reach commercial availability by the end of the decade and should be implemented independently of other process modifications, allowing for adoption as soon as market access becomes feasible.
- Electrification of currently viable technologies—particularly oxidation and carbonisation ovens—should be prioritised. This includes retrofitting existing infrastructure where feasible and ensuring that all electrifiable processes are implemented in new CF production facilities.
- Established energy recovery technologies should be implemented to improve the energy efficiency of carbon fibre production and reduce overall energy consumption. This could include deploying

high-efficiency RTOs for oxidation ovens and incorporating heat recovery systems for high-temperature DFTOs. Prioritising these measures is critical, as energy-saving strategies offer the greatest benefits in the near term while energy-related impacts remain significant.

*Technology development**

- Lower-power electric heating technologies should be developed to further enhance the benefits of electrifying oxidation and carbonisation ovens. While their near-term emissions reduction potential is high, commercial readiness may limit their contribution to decarbonisation. Nonetheless, development should continue given their potential for long-term cost savings and efficiency gains in future CF infrastructure.
- Electrifying exhaust gas cleaning systems is anticipated to be the most technically challenging aspect of CF production decarbonisation. These systems currently account for approximately 25–30% of the total energy demand across PAN fibre and CF manufacturing. Therefore, their electrification is essential. To achieve this, CF producers must actively support the development and integration of electric gas cleaning technologies, which would enable the sector to reduce emissions without depending on the uncertain future availability of green gases (such as BioMethane and synthetic fuels).

** Note that there are many other proposed technology developments for CF production that could support decarbonisation; their exclusion from this proposed strategy is not indicative of a lack of potential but rather reflects current limitations in data availability, technology readiness, or alignment with the near- and mid-term priorities outlined in this roadmap.*

Figure 4 Multi-horizon strategy for CF production decarbonisation

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a life cycle assessment of PAN-based CF production, identifying key GWP hotspots and evaluating decarbonisation strategies. Electrification of CF manufacturing processes, particularly oxidation and carbonisation ovens, offers the most immediate and impactful emissions reductions—especially when powered by low-carbon electricity. However, abatement systems for hazardous exhausts remain a significant barrier, currently accounting for a large share of energy demand and requiring further technological development.

Complementary strategies such as using bio-based acrylonitrile feedstocks, energy recovery systems, and alternative fuels like BioMethane or eMethane may support emissions reduction, particularly where electrification is currently limited. Regional grid composition plays a critical role in the effectiveness of electrification, highlighting the need for site-specific strategies.

A multi-horizon strategy is proposed to guide CF producers through near-, mid-, and long-term decarbonisation actions. This roadmap considers both emissions impact and technological feasibility, offering pragmatic steps toward net zero CF production. While uncertainties remain—particularly around grid decarbonisation timelines and technology readiness—proactive industry action is essential. Early investments in electrification, renewable energy sourcing, and technology innovation will be crucial to reducing reliance on fossil fuels and supporting the transition to low-carbon composite materials.

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